

PRE-ADULT SURVEY TO IDENTIFY THE KEY CONTAINER HABITAT OF *Aedes aegypti* (L.) IN DENGUE ENDEMIC AREAS OF BANTEN PROVINCE, INDONESIA

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Abstract. Key containers are various kinds of water reservoirs where most of dengue vector breeding in them. Identification of key containers is important in order to know what dengue vector population control's target. This study aimed to know the type of containers in the dengue endemic areas of Banten Province and determine the key containers as the main target in vector control. A survey has been done in Cilegon (Bendungan, Panggung Rawi, and Samangraya), Serang (Cipare, Banjaragung, and Unyur), South Tangerang (Bendabaru, Baktijaya, Jalupang). Larvae survey conducted on 100 houses in each location by observing the presence or absence of mosquito larvae in water reservoirs (containers) act as potential breeding sites of *Aedes aegypti* both inside and outside of the house. The survey results were the types of containers, container number, container number with positive mosquito larvae, the key container, and entomology indices in each area. Various types of containers found in nine endemic villages in Banten Province with the most identified containers were buckets, Concrete water storage tanks for bathrooms, and water trays dispenser. A key container in Cilegon and Serang is concrete water storage tanks for bathrooms while in South Tangerang City area is a bucket. Entomology indices in all areas show that all survey areas have a moderate transmission of dengue fever.

Keywords: *Aedes aegypti*, pre-adult survey, key container, dengue, endemic area

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